

ISic1447

I.Sicily inscription 1447

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

tuff

(yellow)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Antonino Salinas, inventory 8777

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Σῶταίρ

2. ὁ εἰμί

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285097

EDR 120818

EDCS 41300046

EDCS 64800264

PHI 175657

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 48 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 62

Gabrics, E. 1927. Il Santuario della Malophoros a Selinunte. *Monumenti Antichi*. 32: 5-419. At 383 no.7 tav.96.5

Grotta, C. 2010. Zeus Meilichios a Selinunte. Rome. At 114-115 no.7 tav.27b

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1447. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354048>